

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness for Ana Tenun Sukarara

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ABSTRACT: Following the implementation of the new norms, such as the relocation of MSMEs, the economy of Indonesia is beginning to recover. Returning to the economy in Indonesia, the implementation of this new normal has caused all nations to recommend economic activities, such as removing social restrictions to encourage people to work. New normal activities are characterized by production and consumption patterns that have an impact on digitalization. This study aims to propose marketing strategies to increase brand awareness of Ana Tenun Sukara, the research method used is non-probability aside from the purposive sampling method, states that non-probability sampling is a sampling technique with a population selected based on its availability or considering it can represent the population while purposive sampling is a sampling technique in which this technique chooses purposive sample that aims subjectively by distributing questionnaires to 200 respondents and processing data with PLS- SEM and analyzing internally with Marketing MIX 4P , STP, VRIO and external companies with 5porter porces, PEST and Competitor analysis. The results of this study indicate that social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand awareness, and social media marketing has a significant positive effect on purchase intention and brand awareness has a significant positive effect on purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Price, Purchase Intention, Social Media Marketing, Weave.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected Indonesia in various facets of life, including health, social, political, and economic. The virus can kill an individual's health immediately. We have entered a new normal in Indonesia, specifically after the COVID-19 outbreak, so that people can carry on with their daily activities while still taking precautions to protect their health, such as wearing masks and maintaining a safe distance.

Following the implementation of the new norms, such as the relocation of MSMEs, the economy of Indonesia is beginning to recover. Returning to the economy in Indonesia, the implementation of this new normal has caused all nations to recommence economic activities, such as removing social restrictions to encourage people to work. New normal activities are characterized by production and consumption patterns that have an impact on digitalization.

Through business digitization, it could be possible for MSMEs to develop their businesses in Indonesia by utilizing various digital platforms. Digitalization has permeated all business sectors because its use is pervasive and accessible to a limited market; thus, there are no boundaries. Social media marketing is one of the digitalizations that can drive the economy and has great potential that micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) can utilize through an optimally open market. MSME actors can utilize social media marketing effectively and appropriately; this is a challenge that must be achieved by MSME actors. Faced with more and more competition around the world, MSMEs need to improve their business skills and abilities in areas like human resources, product innovation, and information technology.

Through social media marketing Online marketing through social media-based websites is used in economic marketing to share information that facilitates the activities of economic producers and consumers. Social media users are able to search for information from online stores of the results of these searches appear as goods, product quality, product specifications, brands, etc. Examples of electronic marketing conducted on social media include Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Shopee, among others. Social media greatly facilitates online consumer shopping and transactions conducted through online media, which can facilitate information search in social media use. Instagram is an application that can sell products and has features such as taking photos, applying digital filters, applying effects to photos, uploading posts or products, and becoming an Instagram business, which can facilitate the business operations of MSMEs. Instagram can be used to market on social media by people who use social media apps on Android, iOS,

computers, etc. In the economy, social media marketing can help with advertising or introducing new products to customers. The goal is to build good relationships between business owners and customers, which makes product development and introduction easier. Ana Tenun Sukarara is one of the cultural arts and traditional fabrics of Indonesia, produced in Sukarara Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara, which are located on the islands of Lombok. Sukarara Village is located approximately 20 kilometers south of Mataram City, the capital of NTB. In terms of colors, patterns, types of materials, and threads used to create it, weaving has a significant historical and technical value. Weaving is one of the cultural heritages that the Indonesian people are proud, which may reflect national identity. Ana Tenun Sukarara is a micro, small, and medium-sized enterprise that uses Instagram for social media marketing and has an Instagram account with the name Ana Tenun Sukarara.

The large number of weaving MSMEs that have joined the online market and various social media platforms has created intense competition between Ana Weaving Sukarara and other sellers for the attention of online buyers, thereby reducing the business profits of Ana Weaving Sukarara, which employs a competitive marketing strategy. Ana Tenun Sukarara has sales targets and this UMKM has a simple, classy, elegant design style to attract the attention of consumers. This is inversely proportional to the current economic situation, especially in the post-covid-19 period, so that currently Ana Tenun Sukarara's UMKM is maintaining its business and strengthening awareness of its customers, such as by means of social media to build customer trust. Mrs. Ana as CEO of Ana Tenun Sukarara explained that the problem that arises in Ana Weaving Sukarara is a lack of brand awareness and their target market is generation Y or women aged 30-40 years so Ana Weaving Sukarara must build and manage existing social media to attract attention customers and build relationships with customers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Analyzing the MSMEs needs The research methodology in exploring business problems explains how to explore business problems and propose marketing strategies to increase Ana Tenun Sukarara's brand awareness by gathering power and analyzing it through PLS or Partial Least Square (PLS) as an analysis technique with structural equation, Variance based mode (SEM) which is continued with the research described from the research design, internal external and how to improve the marketing strategy of Ana Tenun Sukarara's brand awareness. Ana Tenun Sukaraara's business conditions, especially in marketing and promotion through Ana Tenun Sukaraara's Instagram social media marketing because the target market for MSMEs is generation Y who mostly use Instagram then conducts a literature review and analyzes Ana Weaving Sukaraara and analyzes it using external analysis. such as 5porter porces, PEST, competitor analysis and internal analysis such as marketing mix 4p, STP, VRIO analysis

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative methods are used in this study. The data collection method used is non-probability aside from the purposive sampling method. Primary data is data collected by researchers from the first source in this research primary data in the form of questionnaires, Ana Weaving Sukaraara analyzes it using external analysis. such as 5porter porces, PEST, competitor analysis and internal analysis such as marketing mix 4p, STP, VRIO analysis then determining the SWOT and TOWS analysis then to the proposed solution and to the conclusion and recommendation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Consumer Analysis

The validity test is measured from the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value. The AVE value > 0.5 means that the variable is able to describe the variance of each indicator. The reliability test is measured from the composite reliability value. Composite reliability value > 0.6 means that all the question items in this study are reliable. The variables in this study are valid and reliable. The results of the validity and reliability tests can be seen in:

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average Variance extracted (AVE)
Brand Awareness	0,787	0,815	0,874	0,698
Purchase Intention	0,908	0,918	0,926	0,612
Social Media Marketing	0,732	0,865	0,819	0,646

Source : PLS

The R-square value explains the influence of exogenous (independent/independent) variables in explaining endogenous (dependent/dependent) variables. The R Square value can be seen in:

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Brand Awareness	0,267	0,263
Purchase Intention	0,551	0,547

Source : PLS

R squared → 0.267. This model (Social media marketing and Brand Awareness) is only able to explain as much as 26.7% who represent this phenomenon. The remaining 73.3% cannot be represented (there are external variables that affect Brand Awareness). R squared → 0.551. This model (Social media marketing and Purchase Intention) is only able to explain as much as 55.1% who represent this phenomenon. The remaining 44.9% cannot be represented (there are external variables that influence Purchase Intention).

PLS path analysis is performed using smartPLS, the test results are as follows:

The loading factor turns into a T statistic, that is, if the T statistic is > 1.96, it means that the relationship between the latent variables is significant or blue to blue with all the x variables affecting the y variable, which means that it is agreed that the x variable affects y based on a questionnaire question. This study found that social media marketing (SMM) has an effect on brand awareness (BA) with a parameter coefficient of 8.309 and T statistics ±1.96 and is significant at α = 0.05. This is in accordance with research conducted by Samuel & Setiawan (2018) which states that social media marketing has an effect on brand awareness. Social Media Marketing (SMM) has an effect on Purchase Intention (PI), with a parameter coefficient of 9.670 where the T-statistic value is greater than > 1.96 This study is in accordance with research conducted by Priatni, Hutriana, & Hindarwati (2020), which states that social media marketing (SMM) has an effect on purchase intention (PI) and Brand Awareness (BA) has an effect on purchase intention (PI), with a coefficient parameter of 5.545 with a T statistic >1.96 and significant at α = 0.05 so that This is in accordance with research conducted by Dwiyantri et al., (2018) which states that brand awareness has an effect on purchase intention.

B. SWOT Ana Tenun Sukarara

The company's internal analysis is using 4p marketing mix, Segmenting targeting and positioning (STP) and VRIO analysis which shows the advantages and disadvantages of the company Ana Tenun Sukarara and external analysis of the company using 5 porter porces, PEST, and and competitor analysis which shows threats to the company Ana Tenun Sukarara .

Strength Ana Tenun Sukarara (Based on internal analysis)

- 1. Ana Tenun Sukarara has social media marketing

2. Woven products with good quality
3. Woven products with modern motifs
4. Have a weaving place or offline store, namely the village. Sukarara is the center of weaving crafts so it's easy to find

Weakness Ana Tenun Sukarara (Based on internal analysis) 1. Ana Tenun Sukarara is still not known by many people.

2. The price of weaving sold is quite high
3. Lack of a team in managing Ana Tenun Sukarara's Instagram social media marketing.

Opportunity Ana Tenun Sukarara (Based on external analysis)

1. In Indonesia, weaving has many enthusiasts.
2. New competitors are still competing in managing Instagram for weaving marketing.
3. The influence of Instagram social media marketing which offers the same price and quality so that it can be an opportunity for Ana Tenun Sukarara to manage weaving prices.

Threats Ana Tenun Sukarara (Based on external analysis)

1. Competitors easily imitate Ana Tenun Sukarara products
2. Ana Tenun Sukarara provides an opportunity for its competitors
3. Lack of management in Ana Weaving Sukarara's social media marketing which can threaten Ana Weaving Sukarara.

C. Proposed Marketing strategy, marketing through Instagram social media

A. Develop a social media content plan

In planning content on Instagram social media marketing, this is something that is important because in order to attract consumers' buying interest by creating interesting content, content that can explain the products offered, content messages can reach consumers and not flood existing posts. social media by providing a time when photos and videos must be uploaded.

B. Develop promotion on instagram

In making promotions on Instagram, MSMEs need to attention to the discount activities provided to attention to the activity and interaction with consumers on social media marketing Instagram by providing bundle packages and discounted products offered by Ana Tenun Sukarara.

C. Have a social media marketing team

In managing a growing MSME, the existence of a team is an important matter, just as managing social media requires a professional who can manage and market Instagram social media properly to attention to content, quality of content, posts, stories, important information in product marketing in order to increase consumer buying interest.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description in the discussion, the conclusions that can be drawn from this study are social media marketing through Instagram has a positive effect on awareness, brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention and social media marketing has a positive effect on purchase intention such as information that is fast and easy to obtain, user involvement social media marketing in interacting, and effective communication on social media. marketing significant to purchase intention. This shows that social media marketing has a significant influence on purchase intention. It can be seen that there are many internal and external conditions to increase brand awareness among potential customers of Ana Weaving Sukarara, which have made Ana Weaving Sukarara not increase its brand awareness, such as internal factors, namely the lack of special social media marketing management and external factors that arise from competitors and other factors. What influences Ana Tenun Sukarara's brand awareness is by paying attention to good social media management to increase consumer buying interest and how to improve marketing strategies in the Ana Weaving Sukarara market by managing social media with good promotion and good teamwork.

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